

Accepted Manuscript

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PII: S0169-555X(16)30823-6
DOI: doi: [10.1016/j.geomorph.2017.02.026](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2017.02.026)
Reference: GEOMOR 5944
To appear in: *Geomorphology*
Received date: 6 September 2016
Revised date: 28 February 2017
Accepted date: 28 February 2017

Please cite this article as: Mikel Calle, Petteri Alho, Gerardo Benito , Channel dynamics and geomorphic resilience in an ephemeral Mediterranean river affected by gravel mining. The address for the corresponding author was captured as affiliation for all authors. Please check if appropriate. Geomorph(2017), doi: [10.1016/j.geomorph.2017.02.026](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2017.02.026)

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Channel dynamics and geomorphic resilience in an ephemeral Mediterranean river affected by gravel mining

Mikel Calle^{a,*}, Petteri Alho^{b, c}, and Gerardo Benito^a

^a *National Museum of Natural Sciences, CSIC, José Gutierrez Abascal 2, 28006, Madrid, Spain*

^b *Department of Geography and Geology, University of Turku, FI-20014 Turku, Finland*

^c *Department of Remote Sensing and Photogrammetry, Finnish Geospatial Research Institute, National Land Survey of Finland, FI-02430 Masala, Finland*

*Corresponding author. E-mail: m.calle@mncn.csic.es

Abstract

Gravel mining has been a widespread activity in ephemeral rivers worldwide whose long-lasting hydrogeomorphological impacts preclude effective implementation of water and environmental policies. This paper presents a GIS-based method for temporal assessment of morphosedimentary changes in relation to in-channel gravel mining in a typical ephemeral Mediterranean stream, namely the Rambla de la Viuda (eastern Spain). The aims of this work were to identify morphosedimentary changes and responses to human activities and floods, quantify river degradations and analyze factors favoring fluvial recovery for further applications in other rivers. Aerial photographs and LiDAR topography data were studied to analyze geomorphic evolution over the past 70 years along a 7.5-km reach of an ephemeral gravel stream that has been

mined intensively since the 1970s. To evaluate changes in the riverbed, we mapped comparable units applying morphological, hydraulic, and stability (based on vegetation density and elevation) criteria to 13 sets of aerial photographs taken from 1946 to 2012. A detailed spatiotemporal analysis of comparable units revealed a 50% reduction in the active section and a 20% increase in stable areas, compared to the conditions observed prior to gravel mining. Instream mining was first observed in 1976 aerial photograph covering already up to 50% of the 1956 riverbed area. River degradation since then was quantified by means of a LiDAR DTM and RTK-GPS measurements, which revealed a 3.5-m incision that had started simultaneously with gravel mining. Climate and land use changes were present but the effects were completely masked by changes produced by instream gravel mining. Therefore, river incision/degradation was triggered by scarcity of sediment and lack of longitudinal sedimentary connection, creating an unbalanced river system that is still adjusting to the present hydrosedimentary conditions.

Keywords: gravel mining; river degradation; sedimentary connection; ephemeral stream

1. Introduction

Over time, natural river systems in equilibrium, i.e., balanced water and total sediment load (Schumm, 1999), tend to repeat the same planform patterns, mesoscale bedform proportions, channel geometry, and location and type of geomorphic features. Disturbance of equilibrium conditions, caused by factors such as climate, land use changes, and human activities along river channels, may lead to river instability, resulting in river incision, morphological changes, and a lack of longitudinal connection (Kondolf, 1997a; Grabowski and Gurnell, 2016; Marchamalo et al., 2016). Climate and land use changes influence the river system at a watershed scale, changing the

magnitude of water and sediment discharge; whereas instream activities (e.g., aggregate mining) do so more locally (Dufour et al., 2015), changing sediment connectivity and channel geometry (Downs et al., 2013). Understanding or predicting river channel adjustments to these perturbations is always problematic because multiple ‘drivers for change’ may lead to different rates of response or adjustment. Thus, studies of this phenomenon are challenging but necessary to increase our knowledge on the complex interrelationship between hydrology, fluvial geomorphology, and transport capacity of the fluvial environment (Reid et al., 1996; Rozin and Schick, 1996).

In Europe, instream aggregate mining has been one of the main processes responsible for perturbing river environments. The economic development of Europe has involved an increase in the construction of new infrastructures within the continent and thus an increase in demand for aggregate materials. Many rivers contain high quality sand and gravel deposits that are easy to extract and located at a short distance from construction sites. In European Mediterranean countries, the demand for aggregates peaked between 1997 and 2009, during the last housing construction boom. In Spain, construction of residential housing, tourism resorts, and new infrastructures led to a high demand for aggregates in three peak periods: in the 1970s, the early 1990s, and 2008 (just before the financial crisis). Consumption doubled in this latter period, rising from 2000 10^3 tons in 1997 to 4500 10^3 tons in 2007 (source ANEFA), of which ~30% was extracted from alluvial deposits. These are of the same quality as river deposits, but in situ mining is easier because the sites are dry for most of the year.

Fig. 1. Rambla de la Viuda watershed and study reach (red box) that correspond to the area shown in Fig. 5. Fault traces and graben deposits after Simón et al. (2013).

Most studies on the geomorphological effects of instream gravel mining have focused on perennial rivers (Collins and Dunne, 1990; Kondolf, 1994a; Wishart et al., 2008; Martín-Vide et al., 2010; Dang et al., 2014), but owing to its complexity (Segura-Beltrán and Sanchis-Ibor, 2011) only a small number of studies have been conducted on ephemeral streams (Segura-Beltrán, 1990; Kondolf, 1994b; Segura-Beltrán and Sanchis-Ibor, 2011; Downs et al., 2013; Nikolaidis et al., 2013; Segura-Beltrán and Sanchis-Ibor, 2013; Sanchis-Ibor and Segura-Beltrán, 2014). In general, gravel mining triggers changes in channel geometry (Rovira et al., 2005; Martín-Vide et al., 2010), channel incision (Uribebarrea et al., 2003; Rinaldi et al., 2005;), and bedload (Ortega et al., 2014).

Because of the scant number of days with flow in ephemeral rivers, associated with heavy rainfall events, the geomorphic activity of erosion and deposition processes is largely confined to individual events. In addition, the intermittent nature of the

environment favors the lack of real time data such as long-term gaging stations or sediment transport monitoring stations (Reid, 2002). A reasonable solution of it is monitoring morphological and hydrodynamic changes because they have long been recognized as a diagnostic tool in evaluating fluvial landforms, analysis, and prediction of fluvial response (Simon et al., 2007). However, monitoring anthropogenic disturbances with geomorphologic indicators requires long-term proxies to obtain data on the multiple variables and the nature of river adjustments. Fortunately, the sensitivity to disturbance of these geomorphic systems is generally high. In particular, reach-scale research is required to study the river history and impacts of human disturbance (Liébault and Piégay, 2002; Surian and Rinaldi, 2003; Dufour et al., 2015) and to establish the pathways of river recovery and resilience (Kondolf and Piégay, 2003).

Here, we report a study of long-term river response and recovery to instream mining and floods in a representative ephemeral gravel stream, the Rambla de la Viuda, located in a semiarid Mediterranean region. The main objectives were to (i) study the geomorphological changes occurring in the river valley before and after gravel mining using aerial photographs, (ii) identify natural and anthropogenic changes in river geomorphology and sedimentology and the pathways of river channel adjustments, (iii) quantify riverbed degradation, and (iv) provide geomorphological and sedimentological indicators of impacts and system recovery in relation to gravel mining for further application in other ephemeral Mediterranean rivers in Europe and Africa.

2. Regional setting

The Rambla de la Viuda is an ephemeral gravel-bed river draining a catchment of 1523 km² located mostly in the Province of Castellón (eastern Spain). It originates at the confluence of the Montlleó River and the Rambla Carbonera, 36 km upstream of its

river mouth. The study area (Fig. 1 - red box) was located 8 km upstream from the María Cristina reservoir (MC reservoir) and comprised a reach flowing over bedrock with an alluvial valley bottom and a riverbed mainly composed of gravels and boulders.

The river flow entering the study reach is not regulated by reservoirs. Water diversion upstream is negligible, and water flow is the result of the natural rainfall regime. The mean annual precipitation in the watershed ranges between 450 and 600 mm with a main rainy and ‘sometimes catastrophic’ season in autumn (Barriendos Vallve and Martin-Vide, 1998) and a secondary peak between April and May (Camarasa and Segura, 2001). The river flow is mainly associated with intense rainfall events, some exceeding 200 mm in 24 hours. In general, rainfall and flood events have not defined trend that provides clear evidence of variations in the hydrological regime at the study area. According to data from the Castellón de la Plana weather station, an increase in variability and total accumulated precipitation is the most evident characteristic (Fig. 2). Nevertheless, the overall trend in the twentieth century has been a significant reduction in the frequency and the magnitude of major flood events, despite some periods of isolated extraordinary floods (Machado et al., 2011; Benito et al., 2015). The heaviest floods on record occurred in October 1962, October 2000, December 1989, and October 1969, with discharges (mean daily discharge) >640 , 385, 286, and 238 m^3s^{-1} , respectively.

Fig. 2. Annual accumulated precipitation at Castellón city meteorological station since 1851, showing the exceptional variability of precipitation (data source: Spanish Agency of Meteorology, AEMET, courtesy of Javier Sevillano). Red and blue lines express the locally weighted scatterplot smoothing (LOESS) taking into account the surrounding 40 (red) and 10 (blue) years of each point using the regression exposed by Cleveland and Devlin (1988).

Geologically, the Rambla de la Viuda watershed covers two main lithostructural domains, the Iberian Range at its headwaters and the Maestrat graben system in the middle and lower sections (Simón et al., 2013). The basement of the watershed is covered by highly fractured and karstified Mesozoic materials (~80%) and conglomerates (~20%) that confer high permeability to the basin (Bellés Mateu, 1988; Segura-Beltrán and Camarasa-Belmonte, 1996). The last cycle of graben faulting processes took place during Plio-Pleistocene times, when grabens were refilled with tens of meters of alluvial gravel and silt that now feed the present fluvial systems with aggregate sediments (areas of pale color in Fig. 1). The study reach (Fig. 1 – red box) is located between two of those grabens (horst) and corresponds to the natural outlet from the Vall d’Alba graben depression. Because of the placement on this horst area, the river channel width is 2-6 times narrower than it is when it flows on the graben side (over the pale color areas of Fig. 1). This smaller section exerts control to water and sediment flux coming from the entire upper watershed that added to bedrock banks, simplifying

calculation of water and sediment rates for modelling, presence of flood level deposits, and hydrosedimentary interpretations.

The reach has an average gradient of 0.0257 and is mainly composed of a meandering floodway with a river planform that consists of one or more low-flow, migrating channel and two types of channel-scale bedforms and bars. They are basically (i) lateral stationary bars oriented subparallel to the streamflow controlled by hydraulic conditions associated with large floods; and ii) actively migrating, semiperiodically lobate or transversal bars formed during medium or low floods.

3. Methods

The spatial analysis conducted to identify geomorphological changes comprised three main steps: (i) georeferencing aerial images, (ii) mapping the riverbed units, and (iii) analyzing geometry of mapped units.

For the first task, 13 sets of aerial photographs, captured between 1946 and 2012 (Table 1), were georeferenced in the global coordinate system using ArcGIS 10.1, following similar procedures to those described by Downward et al. (1994). Central parts of each photograph were divided into three horizontal strips. For each strip, several ground control points (GCPs) were visually identified and referenced using a 2009 orthophotograph (ICV and IGN, 2012). The GCPs were selected to represent opposite and equivalent points on both sides of the valley, on the riverbed, and around the margins of the river bank. As an ephemeral environment renders the homogeneous distribution of GCPs difficult, a first order polynomial (Affine) function was used to rectify each strip (Downward et al., 1994). Although nonlinear polynomial adjustments usually yield smaller errors around GCPs (Gurnell, 1997), the first-order polynomial

presents more conservative errors along the segment that connects two adjacent points. In addition, it works especially well when the referenced surface is an almost flat surface (floodplain). Lastly, the referenced strips were merged into a mosaic data set in ArcGIS and rasterized into a photomosaic for image homogenization.

Table 1

Aerial photography data sets used for morphosedimentary mapping^a

Year	Flight code	Type	Color	Mean scale	Source	No. of GCP	Pixel size (m)	GSD (m)	RMSE x,y (m)
1946	American Flight "A Series"	AP	B/W	1/47000-43500	CECAF	63	0.49-1	1	1.3-2.2
1956	American Flight "B Series"	AP	B/W	1/33000	CECAF	50	0.86-1	1	1.3-1.8
1967	American Flight "C Serie"	AP	B/W	1/44000	CECAF	55	0.47	1	0.6-0.8
1976	Flight "interministerial" IRYDA	AP	B/W	1/18000	MAGRAMA	105	0.5	0.5	0.8-1.2
1983	National Flight TRAGSA	AP	B/W	1/30000	IGN	39	0.85	0.9	1.4-1.9
1991	Regional Photogrammetric Flight	AP	B/W	1/25000	ICV	145	0.58	0.6	0.8-1
1997	Olive-oil control Flight	OP	RGB	1/10000	ICV		0.5	0.5	<2
2001	American Flight "D Series"	AP	B/W	1:40000	CECAF	103	0.43	0.5	0.4-0.6
2003	Regional Photogrammetric Flight	O	RGB	1/10000	ICV		0.5	0.5	<2
2005	PNOA	O	RGB	1/10000	IGN-ICV		0.5	0.5	<2
2007	PNOA	O	RGB	1/10000	IGN-ICV		0.5	0.5	<2
2009	PNOA	O	RGB	1/5000	IGN-ICV		0.25	0.25	<0.5
2012	PNOA	O	RGB	1/10000	IGN		0.5	0.5	<1

^aCodes: (AP) Aerial Photography; (OP) Orthophotography; (B/W) Black and White; (RGB) 3 bands - Red/Green/Blue- images; (GCP) Ground Control Points; (GSD) Ground Sample Distance; (RMSE) Root Mean Square Error. Organization and project initials: (PNOA) National Plan of Aerial Orthophotography; (CECAF) Cartographic and Photographic Center of the Spanish Air Force; (MAGRAMA) Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Environment; (IGN) National Geographic Institute; (GVA) Valencian Government; (ICV) Cartographic Institute of Valencia.

For the second task, the resulting photomosaics were used to map homogeneous units at a constant scale of 1:1000, suitable for data set comparison. To facilitate photointerpretation (e.g., B/W-RGB differences, light conditions, or presence of

streamflow), the units were defined according to characteristics that remained constant and identifiable over time and in the image data sets, using a combination of geomorphological, vegetation level (cf. Segura-Beltrán and Sanchis-Ibor, 2013), and topographic criteria that presented clearly visible differences (Table 2). First, geomorphic criteria were used to identify the genesis of the river forms (depositional or erosive with natural or anthropic origin), and vegetation levels (no vegetation, small plants to bushes, or the presence of trees) were used to determine activity or stability over time. Lastly, aerial photographs in anaglyph mode (typical red-cyan images to produce the stereoscopic effect) and three-dimensional (3D) glasses were used to identify topographic variations of elements (i.e., peak and low flow bars). These units will be subsequently termed homogeneous morphosedimentary units.

Several methods have been used in river change studies to identify genuine changes based on georeferenced data. For example, Gurnell (1997) reported problems when comparing absolute distance from one set to another, finding that the error when estimating absolute planform change was affected by the individual errors and mapping accuracy of each data set. To avoid this, we compared the total surface of elements instead of comparing absolute distances, i.e., the total amount of square meters that one class of element covers in the studied reach. It then represents the general state of a reach without compromising accuracy (the result from this action is the direct relation between Fig. 3 and Fig. 5). Therefore, given that georeferencing displacements (errors) were areal conservative, the 'bulk surface' characterization errors are estimated to be negligible (Zanoni et al., 2008).

Subsequent result of this mapping is the calculation of mean active sections, conceived as the total active area (Channel + Active Bars) divided by the studied reach's length.

Table 2

Geomorphological mapping criteria applied to define each of the morphosedimentary units; a natural origin is defined as a typical river process, anthropic as produced by human activity, and mixed is the result of a combination of both origins

Morphosedimentary criteria					
Origin	Vegetation cover	River process	Name of morphosedimentary units	Description	Assigned color
Natural	No Vegetation	Erosive	Channel	Bare gravel channels	
		Depositional	Low Active Bars	Low flow gravel bar	
			High Active Bars	Peak flow gravel bar	
	Scantly	Erosive	Abandoned Channel	Vegetated cut off gravel channel	
		Depositional	Scant Vegetated Bars	Incipient vegetated gravel bars	
		Depositional	Vegetated Bars	Mature vegetated gravel bars	
Anthropic	Any Vegetation	No river process	Mined Areas	Extracted areas	
				Piles of blocks left by mining	
Mixed	Any Vegetation	Erosive	Exhumed Rocky Areas	Exhumed bedrock areas	
			Exhumed Old sediment Areas	Exhumed cemented gravels	

Finally, for the last task, a 2009 image data set was used for mapping (using the same criteria explained above), complemented by airborne LiDAR from the PNOA Project (ICV and IGN, 2010). The combination of these two sources of information enabled highly detailed morphosedimentary mapping (1/150 scale). Information on bed elevation was obtained by overlapping the 2009 DTM and the highly detailed morphosedimentary map. In addition, field observations of lateral hanging gravels and bedrock evidence of sediment level were measured by RTK-GPS. From the overlay of all active channels and mined areas, the age of formation of each morphosedimentary element was assigned to the present morphology (Dufour et al., 2015). The resulting ‘incision map’ indicated surfaces that are similar to those in classic terrace maps, which indicates the last time that each element was functionally active.

To compare the altitude of morphosedimentary elements in relation to the channel thalweg, we subtracted the longitudinal profile to render it ‘conceptually horizontal’. Previously, the longitudinal profile was calculated in ArcGIS 10 using the 2009 LiDAR DTM, considering it as the line that contained the lowest topographic points (1-m resolution) following the direction of the flow. To minimize the noise of small topographic variations such as pools, obstacles, and small short-lived bars, the longitudinal profile was smoothed by applying a locally weighted polynomial regression (LOESS, after Cleveland and Devlin, 1988) using the ‘The LOESS Utility for Excel’ (Peltier, 2009) and considering a local interval of 100 m (100 points). In order to establish that limit, mean length of active bars (high and low active bars) was calculated using the ‘Minimum Bounding Geometry’ tool (Tool-reference, 2016) and ‘Rectangle_by_Width’ option in ArcGIS 10. What this tool basically does is adjust a rectangle that better fits the polygon and gives the length of it as an output. Observed minimum length of the stationary bars (~100 m) was the value inserted for LOESS.

Then, a series of cross sections at 10-m intervals perpendicular to bankfull flow were generated and intersected with the smoothed longitudinal profile in ArcGIS 10. The height of the points resulting from intersections was assigned to each section and then joined together in a longitudinal 3D slope on a TIN surface. Finally, the TIN slope was subtracted from the 2009 LiDAR DTM to generate a DTM relative to thalweg. Therefore, topographic variation (e.g., vegetated bars), local incision, and deposition of morphosedimentary units could be evaluated along the study reach.

4. Results

4.1. *Changes in river channel morphology*

The main changes in river channel morphology and dominant fluvial styles associated with self-adjustments were closely related to instream gravel mining and major floods. Three main temporal periods could be distinguished over the last 70 years according to the intensity of human and hydrological activities: reference conditions, disturbed, and recovery stages.

4.1.1. *The morphology of the reference conditions (1946-1967)*

The first two decades (aerial photos from 1946, 1956, and 1967) maintained rather homogeneous proportions of morphosedimentary units. Active stationary bars prevailed (70-80%) over the inactive elements of the river valley (green colors in Fig. 3 and 4: 1946). The average active section (channel and active bars) was 82-92 m wide (from a total mean width of 105 m), infilling the entire river valley at several reaches. This period included the 1962 flood, the heaviest that occurred during the study period, which produced no change in the location or proportions of morphosedimentary elements (Fig. 5, Reference Conditions).

4.1.2. *Channel morphology disturbed by instream gravel mining (1969-2000)*

Mining activity increased after the 1969 flood, resulting in a marked modification of fluvial dynamics and channel morphology. The 1976 aerial set (Fig. 3 and 4) depicted the first visual evidence of human activity in the study reach, which had an increasing impact on fluvial morphology in subsequent years. During this period, the 2-3 m thick upper layer of unconsolidated gravel was completely removed twice, in 1983 and 1997, enlarging the extracted surface to 53% and 46% respectively (see red-

colored areas in Fig. 3 and Fig. 5). Both times, the mining works reached the valley bottom, exposing older cemented deposits (see the bare valley bottom in Fig. 4). The active area of the river valley dropped from the initial 70-80% to 14% in 1983 and in 1997, leaving a mean active section width of 14 and 13.6 m. Mining activities mainly affected the active units, favoring the isolation and steady growth of vegetation on the incipient vegetated bars. These latter increased from 23% to 30%.

Fig. 3. Evolution of morphosedimentary units in top view. The aim of this Fig. is to show the evolution of extracted areas (red). In reference conditions (1946), the river presented small vegetated areas and a multithread channel distribution. In 1976, mining activities began downstream, and 1983 and 1997 showed the largest extension of extracted areas (red). Almost no natural elements remained in the riverbed. After the 2001

flood, recovery was sufficient to replace natural elements, but exhumed areas (pink) showed a marked increase at the margins of the reach. Fig. 4 location corresponds to lobe-shaped bars described in Calle et al. (2015).

Fig. 4. Detail of Fig. 3. This figure points out a sequence of development of an area with lobe-shaped bars (clearly seen at 2012). The sediment connectivity is lost because of instream gravel mining (extraction of

sediment in red). We see how, in 1991 and 2001 photographs, floods are able to recover sediment connectivity but are incapable of reestablish reference conditions, developing exhumation of bedrock and old cemented gravel on banks.

Table 3

Evolution of the total surface (expressed as %) of morphosedimentary units throughout the study period; 'Active areas' column refers to 'Channels', 'Low and high active bars', while 'Stable areas' refers to 'Scant vegetated bars', 'Vegetated bars' and 'Abandoned channels'.

Year	Low and high active bars	Channel	Active areas	Exposed area	Mined area	Scant veg. bar	Vegetated bar	Stable areas
1946	48.7	39.1	87.9	0.0	0.0	8.5	3.6	12.1
1956	44.6	36.6	81.5	0.0	0.0	5.4	13.1	18.5
1967	41.5	38.1	79.7	0.0	0.0	9.6	10.7	20.3
1976	20.7	33.0	55.0	1.4	20.1	9.5	13.9	23.5
1983	6.7	6.6	14.0	2.8	53.3	14.4	15.6	29.9
1991	34.2	22.6	57.9	4.4	15.1	7.7	14.8	22.6
1997	3.9	9.3	13.5	10.6	46.3	12.1	17.5	29.6
2001	35.7	33.5	69.4	5.4	8.1	6.4	10.7	17.1
2003	22.2	26.6	49.1	10.1	4.8	13.0	23.0	36.0
2005	14.3	22.4	37.0	11.1	8.4	17.0	26.5	43.5
2007	11.3	14.9	26.5	13.7	9.2	18.5	32.2	50.7
2009	20.4	17.1	38.3	17.1	6.5	13.3	24.7	38.0
2012	14.9	19.1	34.4	21.4	7.3	10.3	26.6	36.9

The third heaviest flood (1989) occurred during this period of intensive mining, introducing new gravels and activating fluvial landforms toward recovery of initial conditions (Fig. 3 Fig. 4 Fig. 5: 1991). However, extraction of aggregate materials from the area was so intensive that this effect was only temporary, and within six years the same level of extraction as in 1983 was again reached. This is clearly evident in the 1983 and 1997 maps, where the color red (extracted areas) dominates (Fig. 3).

During this period, two new types of units were identified for the first time: (i) 'lobe-shaped bars' and (ii) 'exposed areas' (i.e., old cemented gravels and bedrock

limestones). The exposed areas first appeared in downstream reaches and steadily migrated upstream following the direction of the mining activities. These eroded exposed areas covered 1.4% of the total area in 1976 and 10.6% in 1997 (Table 3).

4.1.3. Recovery and adjustment of fluvial geomorphology under reduced human impact, 2000-2012

In 2000, fluvial landforms were reactivated along the river valley as a result of the second heaviest flood in the instrumental record. New gravel forms once again covered 70% of the river valley and stable areas only constituted 17%, which was almost identical to reference conditions, whereas the mean active section width only reached 72 m. A 2001 map is shown in Fig. 3, depicting new deposition of gravel bars, which restored a natural appearance to the reach.

In the subsequent years (2001-2012), a first period (until 2007) can be distinguished of a rapid increase in vegetation with regular floods, and a later adjustment period (2009-2012) after the 2009 flood (see 2003 to 2007 columns in Fig. 5). In general, active areas dropped from 70% in 2000 to 35% in 2012, and the mean active width decreased to 35 m. Stable areas increased up to 35% in 2012, although extraction areas remained constant (~5 to 9%) owing to a reduction in gravel extraction rates. Despite this, a high rate of exhumation of old gravel and bedrock (from 5 to 20%) was observed over this period (pink areas in

Fig. 3. Evolution of morphosedimentary units in top view. The aim of this Fig. is to show the evolution of extracted areas (red). In reference conditions (1946), the river presented small vegetated areas and a multithread channel distribution. In 1976, mining activities began downstream, and 1983 and 1997 showed the largest extension of

extracted areas (red). Almost no natural elements remained in the riverbed. After the 2001 flood, recovery was sufficient to replace natural elements, but exhumed areas (pink) showed a marked increase at the margins of the reach. Fig. 4 location corresponds to lobe-shaped bars described in Calle et al. (2015).

, 4, and Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Areal changes in the river reach and their relationship to flood events, system stability, and mining activities.

4.2. Incision, bar length, and active section evolution based on geomorphological mapping and airborne LiDAR

Results from the incision map revealed a steady degradation of the riverbed since 1967 (Fig. 6). At present, bars are being deposited 3.5 m below the level of bars deposited under reference conditions (1946-1967).

As can be seen in Fig. 6, the elements that were active in 1946 and 1956 were about 3.5 to 4 m above the present active elements (m.a.p.). The level of the morphosedimentary

elements began to descend in 1967 and fell dramatically to 1.06 m.a.p. in 1983. In 1991, alluvial bed accumulation driven by the 1989 flood raised the level of the gravels up to 1.6 m.a.p.. No new depositional elements were identified in the 1997 photo set (there is no elevation data for this year in Fig. 6), but the bed level was probably even lower than in 1983 (1.06 m.a.p.) according to observed erosional features. The 2000 flood enhanced new alluvial deposition and the channel bed was raised again to 1.10 m.a.p.. Since then, the level of the riverbed has been descending again to the present mean level of active forms (0 m.a.p.), which is ~ 0.7 m above the mean height of the thalweg.

Fig. 6. Graph: Riverbed incision calculated from 2009 topography (red), mean active section (orange), and mean active bar length (grey) in relation to flood events (blue). Picture: incision signatures and hanging gravels in bedrock margins. The upper limit represents the gravel level before extractions ca. 1956-1967. The lower level may correspond to the last cycle of incision (2000-2012).

At the same time, bar length is being reduced more and more only being partly recovered by large floods (Fig. 6). Paying attention on bar length after large floods we observed that active bars were about 140 m long during reference conditions (i.e., after 1962); whereas during gravel mining and adjustment, stages were about 100 m (i.e., after 1989 and 2000).

In addition, active bar length and elevation during reference conditions appeared to be somehow independent to magnitude of events. However, during mining and adjustment stages both parameters have been becoming more and more dependent to the magnitude of events.

5. Interpreting fluvial changes in the context of environmental history

Fluvial morphodynamics are influenced by runoff and sediment flux changes at catchment scale, e.g., land uses and climate, although these may be obscured at reach scale by local actuations like instream gravel mining. Moreover, understanding the impact of catchment-scale modifications may clarify whether the observed local changes are highly connected or completely unrelated to the external variables that can trigger and drive river changes.

No objective evidence of river conditions exists prior to the first photographic flight (1946). However, empirical and proxy data suggest a higher than average rainfall and an unusually high flood frequency and magnitude in the late nineteenth century in southern Spain (Machado et al., 2011). These heavy rainfall and frequent flood events can be assumed to be the conditions for the Rambla de la Viuda at the time, as similar trends were also observed in other Spanish Mediterranean regions (Benito et al., 2008, 2015) and the Pyrenees (Corella et al., 2014).

Concerning land management, the highest human occupation and agricultural use of Mediterranean inland regions occurred around 1900. Thus, it is logical to assume that the Rambla de la Viuda watershed reached a peak of deforestation and agricultural activity at that time. Although documentary evidence of the studied river reach is absent prior to the first photograph, we would expect a scant vegetation, wide, and easily

migrating riverbed, which would agree with the aggradation stage reported for the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries in the Mediterranean region (Segura-Beltrán and Sanchis-Ibor, 2013; Dufour et al., 2015).

During the reference condition stage (from 1946 to 1969), the river maintained a similar configuration (dynamic equilibrium) whereas presenting intense fluvial activity in the river corridor. Climatically, the first half of the twentieth century registered periods of high flood recurrence (1919-1929) but also of scarce events (1935-1945) in Cervol and Rambla Cervera basins (neighboring watersheds studied in Segura-Beltrán and Sanchis-Ibor, 2013). Persistently drier conditions were also described in the southern part of region (Machado et al., 2011). Surprisingly, the heaviest flood in the instrumental record occurred during this period (1962), but only slight changes in the proportion of morphosedimentary units were observed (see Fig. 5). This suggests a river reach in quasi-morphodynamic equilibrium with very large flood discharge magnitudes. During this period, the population decreased by 50% from that recorded in the 1900 census, as people started to migrate to cities. As a result, land abandonment favored the expansion of scrublands and forests, with a presumed reduction in runoff and sediment supply. That could explain the slight increase of vegetated areas observed from 1946 to 1967 and also contribute to stabilization since then.

In the second period (1967-1997), major changes were recorded in the proportions of morphosedimentary units (instability) and intense channel incision, whereas activity of the channel decreases (increase of vegetated bars). The rural population decreased by 15%, following the same trend as the first half of the twentieth century. Although total forest surface increased a 3 to 13%, abandonment of many of the agricultural areas developed scrublands from 1957 to 2007 (Delgado, 2015). Climatically, López-Moreno

et al. (2010) described a stationary or negative trend in the mean rainfall per rain event, although rare extreme events with a long return period may have increased, especially in the autumn in southern and east central Spain (Acero et al., 2010; Machado et al., 2011). Instream gravel mining began in this period and appears to have masked other potential impacts (land use or climate) at watershed scale (similarly to observed; Dufour et al., 2015). In addition, river instability was evidenced by the large morphosedimentary changes that occurred during the 2000 flood. The development of lobe-shaped gravel bars and areas of exposed bedrock is indicative of limited sediment availability.

Over the 2001-2012 period, no major changes occurred in land use at basin scale but aggregate mining was reduced in the studied reach. Meanwhile river degradation continued and new bedrock exposure was mapped. The period started with the 2000 flood that deposited and reconnected with new gravel previous breaks in sediment connectivity. Differences in response of the 2000 flood to similar discharge magnitudes (i.e., 1962 and 1969) indicate an imbalance in hydrosedimentary conditions. Evidence of these conditions is bedrock exposure, bed degradation, and the genesis of lobe-shaped gravel bars. In addition, decrease in the active section has also developed a transitional pattern, displaying wandering-type channels in many areas of the river valley (Fig. 3, 2012 map).

The high temporal resolution of the photo data set over the period revealed the role of small to moderate flows in river degradation. These flows were unable to reconnect sediments in extraction sites (even at smaller mining rates) favoring the isolation of 2000 event bars and producing a rapid colonization by vegetation. These bars are now located relatively higher from the river bottom, and they require higher magnitude flows

to be affected and reworked. Thus, rather than maintaining longitudinal connection of sediment, these smaller flows erode and redistribute the gravel (accumulated at larger floods) and degrade the riverbed producing new exhumed areas.

Minor changes in morphosedimentary units after 2009 (maintained geomorphic activity levels) suggest that the system is reaching a new level of dynamic equilibrium favored in part by the cessation of aggregate mining. Further monitoring is needed here to ensure dynamic equilibrium is observed between the two last photographs (2009 and 2012).

6. Discussion

6.1. *Conceptual evolution of mined reaches and associated elements*

Gravel mining has been one of the principal causes of river degradation and channel narrowing worldwide for more than 50 years in either perennial (Kondolf, 1997; Surian, 1999; Rinaldi et al., 2005; Royira et al., 2005; Simon and Rinaldi, 2006; Martín-Vide et al., 2010) or ephemeral rivers (Collins and Dunne, 1990; Kondolf, 1997; Sandeck and Avila, 1997; Rinaldi et al., 2005; Downs et al., 2013; Segura-Beltrán and Sanchis-Ibor, 2013; Sanchis-Ibor and Segura-Beltrán, 2014). Aggregate materials from instream deposits are usually composed of durable, rounded, and well-sorted gravels that require less processing than any other source (Kondolf, 1997). Consequently, instream mining has become widespread in rapidly developing countries.

The conceptual evolution of such interventions in rivers has been described before, in planview and in cross section, by Kondolf (1997) or Rinaldi et al. (2005) among others, in perennial and ephemeral rivers. However, insights obtained in Rambla de la Viuda suggest new specifications for ephemeral rivers.

If a river is in dynamic equilibrium conditions prior to instream mining, the riverbed slope is regular and the amount of movable sediment is balanced by flows (Fig. 7A). When a specific reach is affected by instream mining, a topographic depression (pit) is created, reducing the available sediment that in turn increases stream power and thus the capacity to transport remaining sediments downstream (Fig. 7B). Gravel pits are usually formed by removing only the upper few meters of alluvium until a hardened level is reached (Fig. 7A). The river's longitudinal profile is thus modified, creating new knickpoints and therefore additional 'discontinuities'. These discontinuities comprise breaks that work similarly to those described by Packard (1974), i.e., as a repeated sequence between headcuts that includes an erosive beginning and a depositional ending. The counterpart of this is the 'knickpoint' and 'deposition within pit' areas described in Kondolf (1997).

Fig. 7. Conceptual evolution and associated elements of instream mined rivers with ephemeral or intermittent hydrology. Exhumation of rock/older deposits and formation of lobe-shaped bars are conceptually explained in cross section and sideways. Left: cross-sectional evolution of a mined reach where formation of microterrace is represented. Top-right: Evolution of a river reach affected by instream mining. We see how, toward downstream, the possible stages are represented and can also be observed in one site over time.

When a period of small to moderate floods (not large enough to recover sediment connectivity), lobe-shaped bars start to develop within depositional environments at the end of discontinuities (Fig. 7C). These elements present prominent, steep (30°), lee side avalanche faces with cross-bedding structures, corresponding to large, subaqueous 3D dunes (Ashley, 1990). These gravel lobes may be oriented transversely to the

streamflow, alternating at either side of the channel with a deep secondary channel formed at the point of contact between the bar front and the valley side. Depending on the magnitude of subsequent flows, lobe-shaped bars will evolve similarly to a fan delta (see conceptual model in Calle et al., 2015). Longitudinally, these gravel bodies are composed of one or more migrating bars (above a bare extracted surface) and a sand/silt cover downstream (also represented in Fig. 7D).

Meanwhile, these small to moderate flows that are not able to carry bedload from upstream reaches dissipate excess of stream power through channel bed and lateral erosion, which results in upstream migration of the knickpoint and the formation of an inner channel (equivalent to the 'trunk channel' described by Bull, 1997). Thus the immediate result of incision is the exhumation of old cemented alluvium and bedrock on which longitudinal grooves develop (Reid, 2002). These exhumed areas typically occur in relation to headcuts and upstream migrating knickpoints that generated discontinuities.

When locally eroded sediment reaches the mouth of the inner channel and enters the flat valley left by extraction (termed sheet flow reach by Baker, 1977), unit stream power, velocity, and turbidity all decrease, leading to deposition of gravels and finer sediments farther downstream (Fig. 7C).

Fig. 8. Extraction site before the event of 2011 (A), where a hardened surface can be seen at the valley bottom. Lobe-shaped bars after the small flood of 2011 (B and C). This field view corresponds to the area covered by 2012 photograph in Fig 4.

As a result, all bedload sediment is deposited within this area, meaning that no movable sediment is available downstream. Once the flow starts to converge again, the excess energy rapidly produces bed degradation. Here, concentrated flow may downcut into the underlying hardened surface (the older substrate), generating a new knickpoint and the beginning of a new discontinuity (Fig. 7D). The sequence is clear and reflects the same principles as those described by Packard (1974) and Bull (1997).

The combination of exhumed areas (e.g., picture in Fig. 6) and lobe-shaped bars (Fig. 8B,C) were observed following the onset of human activities. In addition, these combinations of elements were formed repeatedly over time in areas with sediment connectivity problems (Fig. 4). Therefore, identification of the sequence

(incised/exhumed areas, lobe-shaped bars, and finer sediments) represents field evidence of these anthropic-induced discontinuities.

6.2. *The need of fluvial recovery and the role of floods*

Ephemeral Mediterranean rivers have a 2000-year history of river channel modification and environmental change in the catchment area (Bravard et al., 1997; Boix-Fayos et al., 2007; Thornes, 2009; Dufour et al., 2015), which has modified fluvial dynamic directly and indirectly (Dufour et al., 2015). Quantification of channel incision in the last 70 years has demonstrated that has been ubiquitous in Mediterranean rivers (Table 4).

Table 4.

Some of the most important case studies that reported river degradation and instream gravel mining

River name	Situation	River regime	Basin size (km ²)	River pattern: past/current	Human activity on reach	Bed incision (m)	Source
Gállego River	NE Spain	Perennial	4000	Braided/Single thread	Gravel mining	4 to 5	Martín-Vide et al. (2010)
Tordera River	NE Spain	Perennial	894	Single-thread	Gravel mining	1.5	Rovira et al. (2005)
Rambla de Cervera	E Spain	Ephemeral	339.6	Braided/Wandering	Gravel mining	3.5	Segura-Beltrán and Sanchis-Ibor (2013)
Tagliamento River	NE part of Italy	Perennial	2580	Braided/Wandering to single-thread	Gravel mining	2 to 3	Rinaldi et al. (2005)
Brenta River	NE Italy	Perennial	1567	Braided/Wandering to single-thread	Gravel mining	5 to 8	Rinaldi et al. (2005)
Arno River	Central Italy	Perennial	8830	Sinuuous to sinuous-meandering	Gravel mining and damming	1-3 to 8	Simon and Rinaldi (2006)
Brenta River	NE Italy	Perennial	1567	Braided/Wandering to single-thread	Gravel mining	5 in braided and 7-8 in single thread	Rinaldi et al. (2005)
Piave River	Venetian Plain	Perennial	3899	Multithread planform pattern	Gravel mining, water diversion & damming	2 to 3	Surian (1999) and Rinaldi et al. (2005)
Russian River	California	Perennial	3846	Sinuuous with alternate bars	Gravel mining	3 to 6	Kondolf (1997)
Cache Creek	California	Intermittent	2978	Braided	Gravel mining	4.6 to 8.2	Collins and Dunne (1990)
San Luis Rey River	S California	Ephemeral	1443	Braided/Rectilinear	Gravel mining & damming	3.1 between 1973 and 1993	Sandecki and Avila (1997)
Tujunga Wash	California	Ephemeral	298	Braided	Gravel mining & damming	4	Rinaldi et al. (2005)

Recovery of sediment connectivity and dynamic equilibrium of rivers is essential not only for ecological purposes (Bravard et al., 1997) but also because they respond very differently to similar levels of flood magnitude depending on the proportions of morphosedimentary units (see Fig. 5). For example, the changes induced by continuous sediment extraction in the Rambla de la Viuda River have transformed the river into a

channelized environment, assumed to increase flow velocities during flood peaks, and transferred velocity downstream. These unbalanced conditions are clearly evident before and after the 1989 and 2000 floods, where the photographs show a high sensitivity to floods, i.e., unprecedented morphosedimentary changes. During periods of stability of morphosedimentary conditions (before 1967), the observed changes were small (even though the heaviest flood occurred in 1962) and indicated a very resilient environment. With instream mining and the reference conditions altered, floods produce huge alterations to the system, which means increased morphodynamic vulnerability. Preserving resilient morphodynamic conditions minimizes the river response, which are likely to have a reduction in flood velocities and the magnitude of flood peaks (Downs et al., 2013).

As we know, flooding plays an important role in Mediterranean dryland hydrology and it is therefore important to understand the associated risks and benefits (Barriendos Vallve and Martin-Vide, 1998; Hooke, 2007; Thorndycraft et al., 2008; Benito et al., 2015). This study has demonstrated flooding to be a driver for geomorphological integrity, a term already used with reference to ecological systems (Wicklum and Davies, 1995). A system is deemed to have integrity when it displays organizing and self-corrective capacities that endow it with resilience to perturbation (Hull and Robertson, 2000). Thus, a geomorphological understanding of floods, namely the response and recovery time to reach natural conditions (Pitlick, 1993; Dean and Schmidt, 2013; Hooke, 2016), is essential in restoration schemes based on assisted natural recovery (Sear et al., 1995; Hooke, 2007). For instance, problems of sediment connectivity caused by gravel extraction in the Rambla de la Viuda River were partly overcome during flooding with a threshold discharge over $200 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (1962, 1969, 1989, and 2000). These floods effectively reactivated the sediment supply and fluvial

processes, restoring channel morphology to near-reference conditions similar to channel evolution described by Simon (1989) and Simon and Rinaldi (2006). In addition, flows of around $100 \text{ m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$ (i.e., 2009) slightly mitigated the effects of mining when the intensity of mining was low (e.g., after the year 2000).

Thus, gravel extraction in Rambla de la Viuda has modified the long-term morphodynamics of the river, whereas the largest floods have contributed to river recovery, adjusting fluvial landforms toward new channel conditions.

6.3. *Evaluation of river status and implications for restoration*

Interventions aimed at stream recovery from gravel mining impacts should necessarily include characterization of the previous state of the river (Graf, 1996). Also, realizing that the system is adjusting to new hydro-sedimentary conditions constitute a step forward to propose a realistic target. Assessment of these fluvial conditions can be achieved using geomorphological indicators of river health related to dynamic equilibrium conditions presented in this work. The use of remote sensing data to develop these techniques provides an opportunity to cover broader spatial coverage with higher spatial resolution that may provide objective data to river characterization and management (Downward et al., 1994; Bizzi et al., 2016).

For instance, the relationship between mean bar length and mean active section at different moments (Fig. 9) shows a regression line representing the reference conditions adjusted to the water and sediment discharge conditions at different time intervals. The most heavily altered fluvial conditions (data sets for 1983 and 1997) occurred at times of high aggregate mining activity. The highest bar length vs. active section values (Fig. 9) corresponded to premining conditions (1946, 1956, and 1967), whereas intermediate

values were indicative of regeneration of the fluvial landforms after the 2000 and 1989 floods (aerial photographs of 2001 and 1991).

Bar length vs. active section

Fig. 9. Bar length vs. active section evaluated for the active areas of each photomosaic. Bar length is strongly related to the active section, except for the periods of high mining activity.

According to the observed recovery role of floods and the resilience of this environment, a minimum recovery target for the present river would be to restore at least 70% of the active extent observed in reference conditions, which 'Bar Length vs. Active Section' is plotted inside the recovery box in Fig. 9, following a proportion of 5:3 in length of active forms vs. active channel width. According to incision patterns and sediment reconnection of floods (Fig. 6), bed elevation should be increased by 1 m to reach the proposed recovery target. This would restore morphologies and sediment connectivity to conditions at least equivalent to those displayed during the 1989 and 2000 floods.

Furthermore if applicability of these evaluation techniques is demonstrated in other ephemeral rivers, it could be used not only for economic determination of river status but also to propose a reasonable target to river restoration.

Another tool that might be very useful to identify sediment connectivity problems caused by instream mining is the proposed ‘lobe-shaped bar sequence’. Following the conceptual evolution model of mined reaches we may point out a preliminary map with rivers that would need to care about just identifying the sequence.

A preliminary research of that sequence outside the studied reach revealed that it was present at many places, not only in the whole Rambla de la Viuda River and its tributaries but also in many other rivers affected by instream gravel mining. Reviewing river studies that dealt with river degradation and gravel mining (Table 4) and checking their study case rivers through Google Earth® and ‘the historical imagery tool’ showed the presence of lobe-shaped bars at some of the rivers, suggesting its potential use as an indicator of river degradation and applicability of restoration criteria.

After this positive result, a further search through the Mediterranean region revealed that this sequence was present in more than 20 rivers. In Fig. 10 we proposed a map to show extent of the river degradation problem potentially caused by instream gravel mining. River reaches with incision and bedrock exposure would result from headcut retreat developed from gravel extraction sites, under dominant incision processes and scarce bedload availability. In addition, the lobe-shaped bars suggest a lack of sedimentary connection with redistribution of gravel patches under bedload-sediment-starved conditions. This preliminary diagnosis suggests the need for future studies of river degradation in the Mediterranean region.

Fig. 10. Similar degradation features observed in other Mediterranean rivers. Stars represent the complete sequence of incision, exhumation, and lobe-shaped bars. Incision and exposure represents potential places that may develop the complete sequence in the next flood event.

7. Conclusions

This paper reports the effects of instream mining on an ephemeral river and reveals the direct influence of lack of sediment and sediment connectivity on the type and size of river morphologies. The combined use of aerial imagery and topographic data from airborne LiDAR proved effective for detecting horizontal and vertical adjustments in the study reach, therefore we now recommended to extent it to other river systems. This would be particularly useful for water authorities who wish to analyze and identify rivers with similar problems using remote sensing data. In addition, the proposed recovery target (river conditions after 1989 and 2000 floods) aims to encourage water administrations to include these considerations for river restoration within the context of the European Water Framework Directive. The main conclusions drawn from this study are:

- Of the expected drivers for change influencing an ephemeral river, instream gravel mining proved the dominant factor and completely masked any other impacts such as climate change or basin-scale land use change. In the context of a horst area,

mining activities were responsible for reducing the active river section to <50% of premining conditions.

- Gravel extraction and lack of sediment connectivity resulted in at least 3.5 m of incision. River degradation is still active today, while the river adjusts to the new hydrosedimentary conditions. These problems are not limited to pit sites; the legacy of sediment extraction impacts at river scale long after cessation of mining.
- The changes observed in the Rambla de la Viuda appear to consist of a potentially manageable change and an irreversible degradation — at human scale — considering the predicted future scenarios for Mediterranean regions. Based on recovery produced by the largest floods, a reasonable recovery target would include at least to reach 70% of the active extent at reference conditions, 5:3 proportion of active bar's length vs. active section, and 1 m of bed level aggradation. To achieve effective river restoration, we strongly advise complete cessation of instream mining as reductions have not been sufficient to reestablish sediment connectivity. The remaining 30% (up to 100%) may correspond to irreversible change and would be unstable if such restoration was forced.
- Proposed conceptual model suggests that the combination of exhumed and incision areas and lobe-shaped bars constitute a tool to assess sediment connectivity problems and degradation.
- While a river is being actively mined, the role of floods is critical as the only driver for change that begins the trajectory toward recovery of the system.

- The sequence of riverbed elements preliminarily described in this paper has been identified in a number of Mediterranean streams and may be used as evidence of river degradation. This might help to rapidly identify affected rivers using remote sensing data and might serve to orient future field studies throughout Europe.

Acknowledgements

This paper has been funded by the MINECO through the projects Influence of climatic and environmental variability into paleoflood hydrology and flood hazard in Mediterranean Regions (CGL2011-29176) and Improvements in sedimentary and hydrologic response to environmental and climatic changes in Mediterranean watersheds (CGL2014-58127-C3-1-R). MC was funded by the Spanish FPI scholarship (BES-2012-056723). PA was funded by Academy of Finland (COMBAT project, grant number 293389). Special thanks to the ICV and IGN (and their employees Margarita Caletrío and Carmen Salado) for the aerial photographs, to Javier Sevillano for shearing the precipitation data, to reviewers who have kindly improved the paper through their very constructive comments, and to the editor, Dr. Richard A. Marston, who has supported our work through his advices and help. Thank you all for your help and contribution with my first experience as corresponding author, dealing with the publication process of the first paper of my PhD. I will fondly remember it.

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